

The Basic Paradox – The Event

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Live Text and videofeeds

Terence Love keynote speaker

This interview comprised the introduction and opening session to a new virtual conference going out live internationally in December 2002 from the Profile Intermedia 5 conference during 6 7 8 December, Messe Centrum, Bremen.

»The basic paradox« enabled the audience to participate as well as presenting several »paradox« related workshops and seminars for the profile intermedia/paradox audience.

This included live-chat, live-videoconference and live-broadcasting of pictures from Bremen and Halle/Germany via the internet.

project-partner: [Hochschule für Kunst und Design Halle](#)

Transcription of Introduction and first keynote presentation - Dr. Terry Love of Edith Cowan University

Alles so neu hier! Ist was abgestürzt?

23:17:27 Bremen enters this room

23:40:13 [\[Bremen\]](#) Hallo

----- The messages that have been sent today start below -----

00:01:38 [\[Translator\]](#) Hi

00:19:58 [\[jank\]](#) please visit.. [<http://www.thebasicparadox.de..>](http://www.thebasicparadox.de..>) download the flash player 6... and enter the video chat.. use dsl if possible...

00:22:02 tlove enters this room

00:22:36 [\[jank\]](#) welcome mr. love.. nice to see you...

00:22:50 [\[tlove\]](#) Hello everyone

00:22:56 [\[Translator\]](#) Hell mr love

00:24:12 [\[jank\]](#) hi terry ..i hope you remember me.. this is jan kurpjoweit from germany.. it's a little bit time ago since we've talked...

00:25:30 [\[tlove\]](#) Hi Jan good to hear from you. I'll have to drop out for a minute to sort my system out

00:25:43 hasdogan enters this room

00:26:25 [\[jank\]](#) don't worry.. we've now 24 hours..to discuss the basic paradox.. ;-)

00:29:18 [\[Translator\]](#) sorry, i've got some problems using i-explorer or opera as browsers

00:52:10 [\[jank\]](#) what you see... is dr. terry love..

00:52:28 [\[jank\]](#) nice to see you mr. love

01:13:00 [\[Nita\]](#) hello houston...

01:15:45 [\[jank\]](#) well ... ken friedman (i guess) said .. the "design" (specially those interface design) is better now than 10 years ago... i'd like to say..that this is an good

example....that this is not the case.. ;-)

01:16:25 halle enters this room

01:16:51 [uyl] the "designs" might be better but for the "design" this isn't true

01:18:10 [Bremen] hello terry, this is jonas

01:18:25 [tlove] Hello everyone

01:18:37 [tlove] hi Jonas

01:18:44 [dg] hi!

01:18:56 halle2 enters this room

01:19:20 [Bremen] hi terry, lets go to the next question: can you give a summary regarding your position to design foundations

01:19:43 [tlove] Do you want to ask any of the interview questions here, Jonas?

01:21:09 [Bremen] yes, lets start with question 2

01:21:13 [Jens] what is the neurophysiologic view on design paradox?

01:22:04 [tlove] I'm interested in basic concepts that make sense with the concepts of other - more established -disciplines. Though I'm very aware that making sense out of designing as a human activity will likely suggest changes to theories of other disciplines

01:24:04 [Bremen] the first part is an interview

01:24:15 [tlove] On the neurophysiological side, I'm suggesting that design theory benefits from separating internal aspects (what I use the term 'designing' for) and external aspects - which I, in line with many others use 'design process'.

01:25:23 [Bremen] why do you think that designing, the understanding of designing benefits from neurophysiology?

01:26:57 [Bremen] terry, isn't a kind of reductionism?

01:27:05 [tlove] I suggest that a simplifying concept is to the idea of a human internal process 'designing' that is at a similar primary level to 'thinking' and 'feeling'. That this is a useful start for building theory. The psycho neuro-physiological stuff contributes here.

01:28:24 [Bremen] thinking, feeling, designing, this is the whole of human life. you are aiming at a theory of everything?

01:29:19 [tlove] No, I don't see it as a reductionism. Rather, its starting to question, at a deep level, the very well established theory positions from which the idea of reductionism is coined

01:30:42 [Bremen] which level are you thinking of?

01:30:58 [tlove] Currently, design theory is a serious mess. Designing involves lots of human internal and external activities - so naturally to build good foundations for design theories, these things have to be addressed

01:31:06 [Bremen] atomic, quantum?

01:33:01 [Bremen] why do you think that going to "deeper" levels brings deeper insight?

01:33:19 [tlove] This is an unusual moment in human history. To this point for 4-5000 years we have had to try to make theories about human activities by looking at the externals. A bit like trying to work out the code for a word processing software program by looking at the documents someone has written using the

01:34:25 [tlove] program. The big change is that for the first time in human history we are going to be able to look more directly at the internal processes. To start to use this new knowledge is only as reductionist as humans are intrinsically deterministic.

01:35:34 [tlove] Deeper levels. Mmm. The aim at this point is to try to sort out which sorts of core concepts are useful for building a theory-basis for understanding the human activity of designing.

01:36:51 [Bremen] which level are you aiming at? each level works with different models, languages, theories

01:37:24 [Bremen] why do you think that these models are easier to decipher than the phenomenal level?

01:37:44 [Bremen] how to "read" an MRT-Image?

01:38:13 [Bremen] do you hope to find a "style neuron"?

01:39:30 [tlove] I've spent twenty years looking at building design theory in terms of integrating across the levels. I'm now beginning to feel that the solution lies in making choosing clear definitions of key terms. Not 'what is design' but rather 'What is the epistemologically best use to which we can define the

01:41:12 [tlove] Phenomenological analysis is interesting. In theory (!) it should be able to encompass many of the necessary concepts. In practice, it presents many problems for building generalisable theory that is of easy use by others. It also doesn't have the scope to address many key issues.

01:42:37 [tlove] fMRT is simply a tool - not of direct interest in building theory.

01:43:36 [Bremen] but you have to interpret MRT images just as you have to interpret phenomena

01:44:13 [tlove] The new kinds of theory that are emerging are perhaps best sketched out in Anthony Damasio's works in 1994 and 2000. These look at the underlying human processes that underpin how we use feelings in our agency

01:46:08 [tlove] What is a 'style neuron'?

01:47:33 [Bremen] it is the neuron where style aspects are processed in the brain. you pretend to gain insight in these processes by observing the brain

01:51:15 [tlove] Mmm, 'style neuron' is a bit simple. There are a lot of highly interlinked processes, mainly associated with feelings, that are involved in even the simplest human action like thinking to draw a single line of a particular style.

01:51:25 [Bremen] terry, I think there are ever new black boxes showing up

01:53:51 [tlove] Only if you want to sit with the 'old' epistemology foundations that theorise about human actions on the basis of conceptions only based on external observations. Time for a change. We are humans and we function - doesn't have to be magic.

01:59:14 [Bremen] do you think that crossing the skin from external to internal observations changes to a new epistemological category

02:06:05 [übersetzer] by setting a definition of internal processes we already finished the description. How to understand about 4500 years of external observations while thinking about the individual?

02:06:07 [Bremen] after this difficult start I would like to open the general debate.

02:06:44 [tlove] Being able to get a better idea of the internal processes is helpful to clarifying many issues that we've made up concepts to try to make sense of over the years. - concepts like knowledge, 'meaning', 'style'

02:08:20 [tlove] Hi Übersetzer - great question - to the core of the problem

02:10:54 [tlove] Mm in all of this I feel its very very important to keep separate 'reductionism' and 'biological determinism'

02:11:39 [rosan] hi terry, you said in your article that 'research into designs# can be the topics of investigation within existing traditional disciplines. But isn't it the same can be said of 'research into creating designs'?

02:16:31 [tlove] Hi Rosan, I feel that traditional disciplines are limited in the scope of what they can address in building theory about designing (human non-routine activity leading to the devising of a plan) There is room for a specific field of Design Research' that doesn't overlap with them

02:19:30 [aravena] terry, what kinds of limitations are you talking about?

02:19:39 [rosan] but a topic can be studied under different fields, through different lens; doesn't what distinguish a field is a particular view on interpreting and interacting with the world that leads to a particular body of knowledge?

02:23:53 [übersetzer] if we found the answer for "creating design" doesn't it automatically lead to the knowledge of how to destroy design?

02:24:03 [jank] i'm sure that the answer of creating designs is a neuro answer.. this is somehow very logical..

02:25:54 [tlove] Hi Aravena, I'm simply pointing to the fact that theoretical perspectives and methods such as phenomenological analysis are tools and as such have a limited repertoire. Some things can be addressed by them and some things not. Even then, they bring a particular viewpoint with its slant.

02:29:30 [Bremen] terry, is it easier to interpret an MRT image than a designer's behaviour?

02:31:31 [aravena] well, terry I think that from phenomenology design becomes a little more deep than other viewpoints (as science, for example)

02:31:44 Jens exits from this room

02:33:09 [tlove] Interpreting a designer's behavior requires a sound theory base. So far we've presumed and assumed that everyday or social paradigms of analysis have been fine for analysing designers' behaviour with the intent of improving designed outcomes. I am suggesting that this now needs to be problematised.

02:35:07 [rosan] sure, it needs to be problematized, terry, but from which point of view?

02:35:32 [tlove] In problematising ways of looking at designer behavior, it starts to present some serious difficulties - especially in building coherent theory that includes internalised aspects of feelings - important in designing.

02:38:06 [tlove] Oops, Hi Aravena, I tried with phenomenology to bridge engineering, social, environmental and ethical explanations of designing. I found it wasn't sufficient - and doesn't really offer good means of making theory that is broadly useful. As a tool for exploration it was better than for making good theory

02:39:25 [tlove] I agree Science is insufficient - it specifically precludes subjective perception and experiences. I found that simple post-positivist was the most helpful

02:40:07 [aravena] ok, now I could understand you...

02:40:30 [rosan] terry, are you seeing phenomenology as a METHOD or a VIEW?

02:40:54 [aravena] you are going to explain design throughout a post-positivist approach... I'm wrong?

02:41:45 [tlove] Hi Rosan, As a tool. It offers some methodic structures and it requires a specific place to view phenomena.

02:43:45 [tlove] Hi Aravena, More than I found post-positivist (à la Popper) was a useful theory frame in which to locate many other methodics and theory structures. It doesn't do everything. . .

02:44:21 [aravena] ok...

02:44:30 [tlove] which paper of Coyen et al.

02:48:20 [aravena] ummmmmmm... device's phenomenology (a study of electronic drawing board)

02:50:57 [aravena] in this paper there is a phenomenological "analysis", but I think phenomenology is very rich as a view, not as a tool

02:51:27 [tlove] Rescuing CAD from Rationalism might be the paper?

02:52:53 [aravena] The 2002' Special issues on Philosophy of Design...

02:53:22 [aravena] from Design Studies Journal (Gall guest editor)

02:54:09 [rosan] terry, do you think that to ground design theory on research into human psycho-neuro-physiological processes BY ITSELF distinguish design as a field?

02:59:28 [tlove] Rosan, I think that doing some careful work on definitions is the first thing. I'm suggesting defining 'designing' in a particular way that separates it from design process. That way, we can look at what happens inside humans separate from the social and other analyses.

03:00:56 [aravena] but, how could we to separate designing from their own process? Do you think that is possible?

03:01:12 [tlove] The psycho-neuro-physiological stuff is needed for the first - it does also have some implications for the second - particularly if a mediated systemic view is taken of how humans interact.

03:01:40 [aravena] there is not a human separate from their lived world... that is phenomenology

03:03:20 [tlove] Aravena, I suggest defining 'designing' as an internal human activity similar to but different from thinking and feeling. 'Design process' can be regarded as any process that includes at least one individual act of 'designing' -alongside other activities such as perceiving or drawing or communicating

03:04:19 [Bremen] terry, couldn't you just simply give us an example of what you mean by all this, I mean, a concrete, "Touchable\$ Casus?

03:06:21 [Bremen] What is your utopian fantasy? how would this connection "Neuroscience-Design" work if it worked?

03:07:06 [aravena] I Think you need some ground for that, and this ground put the human as having separates internal and external states...

03:07:42 [aravena] may anything a little more rational... like cognitive sciences

03:08:38 [rosan] but terry, isn't your proposed approach to define design, another discourse - another scientific view on design rather than a design view?

03:11:28 [Bremen] terry, if you are right, how would designing work in 100 years?

03:14:34 [tlove] One of the problems with designers as theorists is that they are good at devising new things. What is needed in terms of building a coherent theory foundation for a field of design research and theory making is some careful choice about which definitions are best in epistemological terms

03:15:17 [tlove] This is especially important to make theories of designing comport well with theories of other disciplines.

03:16:36 [aravena] I agree with you Terry, but I think you have an epistemological choice, that is not consensual for building a coherent theory of design

03:17:26 [tlove] Mmm Touchable, concrete, utopian, fantasy of design in 100 years? My perspective is that designing, devising plans to change the future, is a core human activity. I guess we'll keep on doing it! I thought we were talking theory making.

03:19:29 [aravena] but is your choice, and I will be alert for your very rich comments on theory

03:19:33 [rosan] aravena - could you rephrase your last point please?

03:19:50 [Bremen] if everything remains as it is, your theory is just for fun?

03:20:57 [aravena] It's a little late for me and I hope meet you today night...

03:21:40 [tlove] Good night Aravena. Many thanks for your insightful comments and questions.

03:22:13 [aravena] and a hope a high level debate not just ironies (do you heard Bremen)...

03:24:06 [tlove] Bremen, a key issue for many nations is social and economic development. That is directly affected by design infrastructure that improves the

efficiency and effectiveness of the way that designs are produced. Improving design theory foundations is part of the support for improving design infrastruc

03:24:09 [\[Bremen\]](#) a high level debate would require a high level neuro physiologist

03:25:54 [\[tlove\]](#) Its late. I must take a break. Many thanks to everyone. I have very much enjoyed the debate and interview. Look forward to participating later.

03:26:25 [\[Bremen\]](#) bye terry - thanks - jonas

03:27:01 [\[aravena\]](#) rosan, I think that to build a theory or ground of design it is not necessary to use any separation between subject and object, for my this is a epistemological choice, not a true ground. When terry talk about internal and external activities it is clear for me that there is a choice the puts...

03:27:02 [\[rosan\]](#) thanks terri and others, i enjoyed it too.

03:28:11 [\[aravena\]](#) subject and object distant one from others

03:29:07 [\[tlove\]](#) Bye!!

Clipped – next Keynote